

KHUSHANZAMON-NATIONAL ETHNOGRAPHIC FOLKLORE ENSEMBLE

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Abstract. *It was written a little more seriously, since it was for a scientific article, I looked at the facts.*

Key words: *KhushonZaman, Uzbekistan, Alla.*

ХУШАНЗАМОН-НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ЭТНОГРАФИЧЕСКИЙ ФОЛЬКЛОРНЫЙ АНСАМБЛЬ

Аннотация. *Написано чуть более серьезно, так как это была научная статья, я посмотрел на факты.*

Ключевые слова: *ХушонЗаман, Узбекистан, Алла.*

Today, we can say a number of positive things about the "Khushon Zaman" folklore-ethnographic folk amateur team, organized under the House of Culture, Navbahor district, Navoi region. The brightest and most exemplary of them is known as the folk dasta.

In accordance with the order of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2007, the "Khushon Zaman" folklore ethnographic team was recognized as "People's Amateur Team" for their meritorious service of preserving our eternal values, which are the essence of our spirituality. "Khushon Zamon" folkloric ethnographic folk amateur group is enriching its repertoire with new folk oral examples every year.

The artistic group shows its performances at district-level festivals and fairs and gradually comes to the public's attention. Since 1989, they have been actively participating in regional and republican level examinations and have been taking honorable places. In 1995, "Huybale", which was staged by the team on the basis of folk dances, now forgotten, that is, the dance of the groom's servants visiting the bride's house, will be shown on the TV and radio channel of Uzbekistan.

With this, the traditions existing in the district are brought to the attention of the general public. Until 2000, the team was led by Rana Akhmedova, a passionate culture worker. Due to Aya's incomparable service, the team has become famous in the republic during these past years. With the initiative of that person, our eternal values, lapar and alyars, which are being forgotten, and our traditions, which are the foundation of our spirituality, were restored.

In the course of their activities, the team collects examples of folk art and preserves them for centuries and makes their contribution to the younger generation.

Chorlov
My child said,
Jam called the cup water.
He said, "Let me go to Kotanda."
"Tiramo" said my wedding.
Togora head uncle,
Momo of Kaivanisi.
Servant aunt and uncle
Let there be more weddings, my child.

"Khushon-zamon" folklore-ethnographic folk amateur ensemble was established in 1987 by the director of the village culture house "Gigant" (now "Istiqlal") belonging to the central culture house of the district by the director of this village culture house (deceased) Rana Aya Akhmedova. The ensemble consists of 22 members. The ensemble performs the forgotten folk thermals characteristic of its region and the rituals and rituals from the village of Arabkhana: Osman Baba Kholov, Tashbibi Khakberdiyeva, Rajabgul aya O'sarova, from Karojan:

Saodat aya Toirova, from Beshrababad: Ruqiya aya Namozova, (deceased) Ravshan Baba Goyibnazarov today recorded the songs of young folklorist poets Gulchiroy Soyilova and Mukhayo Nazarova and included them in their repertoire. In the course of its activity, the ensemble participated in district and regional competitions several times and became prize winners. Here we will quote the information one by one: in 1989, he took part in the competition held within the framework of the III-All-Union folk art festival in Galasia, Bukhara region, and won the first place.

Play it, sing it, open your arms,
Sing from high happiness, from a high throne.
Let the ancient earth tones sing,
Play with fun and excitement.
The melodies of my motherland are old-fashioned,
Pray that no grudge will touch us.
May the melodies of Uzbek never die,

Don't let your eyes touch this dear Motherland.

In 1993, the songs "Alla" and "Yor-yor" of the folk groups of Kyziltepa district took the first place in the regional competition. In 1995, the "Huy ballet" ceremony of the ensemble was filmed for the "Zilol" program of the Uzbek television, and the program is preserved and broadcast in the "Golden fund" of the television until now. In March 2005, he took part in the "Korpa dozon" ceremony at the regional head of the folklore festival and was awarded with a II-level diploma.

In May 2005, he took part in the 4th Open Folklore Festival "Boysun Bahori" and was awarded with a diploma and commemorative gifts by the organizers of the festival. In July 2005, members of the ensemble Norjon Orokova, Lutfulla Bobomurodov took the proud 1st place at the regional stage of the I-Republica screening festival of "Lapar va Olan" performers, took an active part in the Republican stage, and were awarded an "Honorable Label" by the organizers of the festival.

In October 2006, the ensemble's theatrical program based on the rituals "Korpa dozon" and "Huy ballet" was filmed and broadcast several times for the show "Across the Country" broadcast by Uzbekistan TV. On March 30, 2007, the ensemble took part in the regional head of the folklore festival "Navkiron Samarkandga Tazim", held in connection with the "2750th anniversary of the city of Samarkand", and was awarded with the II-level diploma of the festival.

On April 2-5, 2007, the participants of the ensemble N. Orokova and L. Bobomurodov took part in the traditional II-Republic exhibition festival of performers "Lapar and Olan" held in the city of Namangan and were awarded the second place and the second degree diploma. According to the decision of the Ministry of Culture and Sports Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2007, the title of "People's amateur team" was awarded to the folk-ethnographic team "Khushon Zaman".

In 2008, the ensemble's theatrical program "Koklam Soginchi" was filmed and broadcast on regional television on March 17. In addition, the "Khushon Zaman" folklore ensemble participates in all cultural and public events, pageants and festivals organized in the district and region with its new and colorful programs.

On May 4-5, 2013, he participated in the traditional culture festival "Sounds of Centuries-2013" with the program "Singing Ancient Traditions". He received the "Laureate diploma" of the festival. "Khushon Zaman" folklore-ethnographic folk team, organized under TMMU, participated in the 19th Tashkent international tourist fair "Tourism along the Silk Road" held on October 7-10, 2013 in Tashkent.

Bukhcha
My mother-in-law,
My mother's little one,
I don't want to carry
I can't sleep without you.
In the silk address,
On the face of a silk flower,
My big boy, my big boy,
The small one is a small one.
Around my forehead,
learn from Ptolemy,

Collecting dowry little by little,
Let's get ready for matchmaking
give me a bride my god
I have a lot of flowers,
fill in my guess
I'm fine.

On March 15, 2014, Saodat Ormonova, the senior editor of the cultural-educational and artistic recreation program of the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan, filmed the ensemble's program "Navroz navolari" at the Sarmishsay resort, which is still being broadcast by Uzbekistan TV.

On March 4, 2015, in the concert hall of the Children's Music and Art School of the District No. 11, a ceremony called "Beautiful World, Honorable Woman" was held in cooperation with the district department of the "Mahalla" Charitable Public Foundation, the District Department of Culture and Sports Affairs, in the concert hall of the District 11 Children's Music and Art School. "Khushon Zaman" folkloric ethnographic folk amateur team participated in the holiday event with its program "Momolar allasi - feeling of love". District on March 18 at the "Navbahor" playground in the district center

"Koklam visit is beautiful Navruz mubarak" was staged in cooperation with the administration of the Ministry of Education and Culture, district vocational schools, the district department of the "Mahalla" Charitable Public Fund, the district department of the "Kamolot" YoIH, the "Barkamol Avlod" children's center, and the central culture and recreation centers of the population. At the holiday celebration, he pleased all viewers with his program "Elga Navroz toy keldi". On April 20-22, 2015, at the Academy of Arts of Tashkent, Uzbekistan

"Fine and Applied Arts" festival was held in cooperation with the Union of Artists in connection with the "Year of Honoring the Elderly". "Khushon-zamon" folklore ethnographic folk amateur group participated in the festival with its program "Singing ancient traditions" and was awarded with a diploma of the Union of Artistic Artists of Uzbekistan. On March 18, 2016, Beshrabort Cultural and People's Recreation Center held the "Navbahor" playground in the district center "You are an ancient treasure, the real priceless Nowruz!" "Khushon Zaman" folkloric ethnographic folk amateur team presented their charming tunes and songs "Ayyom, who became my mother's bride". On March 26, in the concert hall of the Regional Department of Culture and Sports Affairs, the performers of "Alla" for the People's Artist of Uzbekistan Habiba Okhunova award "Khushon" at the regional stage of the Republican competition.

"Zamon" folklore ethnographic folk amateur team participants and Kh. Muhammedkulova won the prize for the performance of "Alla" characteristic of the region and for skillfully performing the most ancient values, traditions, customs of our people on stage, and the I-level diploma of the Regional Department of Culture and Sports Affairs. was awarded and won a ticket to participate in the Republican stage of the competition. On March 31, in the "Alisher Navoi" theater of Namangan region

"Alla" performers took part in the final stage of the republican competition, Kh. Muhammedkulova and "Khushon Zaman" folklore ethnographic folk amateur team took part and received the I-level diploma of the scientific methodical center of folk creativity and cultural-educational affairs of the Ministry of Culture and Sports of the Republic and was awarded with

souvenirs. On April 20, in the concert hall of the Regional Department of Culture and Sports Affairs, the order and regulation of the Ministry of Culture and Sports Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 393 dated March 25, 2016 and

Based on the order of the Department of Culture and Sports Affairs of Navoi region dated April 1, 2016, in order to preserve our national values, pass them on to the next generation and further enrich them, to widely promote the alla genre, which is a masterpiece of folk art, among the population, especially the growing young generation, and popularize it among young mothers. The stage of the republican festival was held at the festival "My mother told me". Participant of the ensemble N.Saidova participated in the festival with the song "Alla" typical of our region.

He won the award in the category of "Honorary performer" and was awarded with souvenirs. On May 5, in the center of the company farm "Oltinsoy" of the Khatirchi district, on the occasion of the 25th anniversary of the State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, within the framework of the republican festival "Bakhshilar yurtni kuylaydi" "Bakhshilar sings the country" 2nd traditional festival "Singing old traditions" consisting of folk songs, songs and folk songs typical of our region " participated and received public applause.

Kulta Pushak

When my daughter becomes a bride,

When he is happy like the moon.

When the time comes,

I wore a dress.

Goodbye this head,

May it not fade away.

Age to face

I wore a dress.

May your tongue be full of sugar,

May his hair be willowy.

Now let him play, laugh,

I wore a dress.

Good luck to the boys and girls,

I am a loving mother.

Be a great mother-in-law,

I wore a dress.

Jamalak

Forty girls

His hair is on his waist.

Come on guys

Put it on jamalak.

Little by little,

Hair gradually.

To girls with jamalak,

Everyone is excited.

come on girls

Telling a fairy tale,

It suits you so well
Jamalak with glasses.

If we look at the last year, we can see that the new repertoire of the team was popular. For example, every year dedicated to Navruz national celebrations "Hello, Navruz - a day of renewal, kindness and dignity!" under the motto "Today is Navruz in a paradise full of flowers."

In Uzbekistan!" A popular election was held. The performance of the team certainly made a warm impression on the audience. Also, a concert program was presented in the "Dul Dul" neighborhood as part of the "Green Space" nationwide project. On the occasion of International "Family" Day, "Family is the eternal state of mankind!" received the applause of the audience with their performances at the festive event. "International goldsmithing and jewelry" festival held in Bukhara on May 21-24, 2022

"Khushon Zaman" ethnographic folk hobby group, organized under Navbahor District Culture Department, participated with its program and was awarded with "Thank you note" and souvenirs from the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Bukhara Regional Department of Culture.

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